

Shared Access Terrestrial-Satellite Backhaul Network enabled by Smart Antennas: SANSA

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Abstract—This extended abstract gives an overview of the research activities that will be carried out in the SANSA project, funded by the EU under the H2020 Programme. In particular, it details the objectives and benefits of the proposed spectrum efficient self-organizing hybrid terrestrial-satellite backhaul network, and briefly describes the technologies that will make this solution possible.

Keywords—Backhaul network, terrestrial-satellite shared access; self-organizing network; smart antennas

I. INTRODUCTION

The changes in user trends and the appearance of new applications in recent years resulted in a huge increase of mobile traffic worldwide. Current predictions state that data requirements will increase up to 1000 times by 2020 [1], with 2/3rds being video traffic. Out of the required 1000x increase in capacity, 10x is expected to come from increased spectral efficiency for which new waveforms and technologies such as Massive MIMO are being proposed; 10x from the use of additional spectrum, in which millimeter wave band would play an important role; and the other 10x is expected to come from reduced cell sizes, thus from dense small cell deployments. However, these access technologies, and specially the small cell scenario, impose new challenging requirements to backhaul networks which require novel solutions in order to avoid becoming the bottle neck of future mobile networks.

In this framework, the European Commission is funding the SANSA (Shared Access Terrestrial-Satellite Backhaul Network enabled by Smart Antennas) research project [2] under the HORIZON 2020 Framework Programme. The aim of SANSA is to boost the performance of mobile wireless backhaul networks in terms of capacity and resilience while assuring an efficient use of the spectrum. To this end, SANSA proposes a spectrum efficient self-organizing (SON) hybrid terrestrial-satellite backhaul network based on three key principles: (i) a seamless integration of the satellite segment into terrestrial backhaul networks; (ii) a terrestrial wireless network capable of reconfiguring its topology according to traffic demands; (iii) a shared spectrum between satellite and terrestrial segments. This combination will result in a flexible solution capable of efficiently routing the mobile traffic in terms of capacity and energy efficiency, while providing

resilience against link failures or congestion and easy deployment in both rural and urban areas.

II. SANSA VISION

Fig. 1 depicts a deployment example of the hybrid terrestrial-satellite network targeted in SANSA. The terrestrial segment resembles a wireless mesh network in which each node can communicate with many of its neighbors. This feature is enabled by equipping terrestrial nodes with smart antennas with beamforming capabilities, instead of the traditional fixed parabolic reflectors. In addition, hybrid nodes capable of communicating with both other terrestrial nodes and a satellite are spread throughout the whole network. In these hybrid nodes, a hybrid network manager, which constitutes the second key enabling component of the SANSA solution, allows the efficient use of all the network resources in order to improve capacity and energy efficiency.

Fig 1. Hybrid backhaul network proposed in SANSA

The three basic principles supporting the SANSA backhaul solution are further analyzed next.

A. Hybrid Terrestrial-satellite network

The integration of the satellite component with the terrestrial backhaul network not only provides the evident benefits in terms of easy and cost efficient network deployment in rural or remote areas, but it also enables data off-loading from terrestrial network hot spots, which in turn results in

overall capacity increase. Besides, it also provides a new path for routing the traffic that increases the network resilience against link failures. Note that this architecture can be very useful also in disaster relief situations where parts of the terrestrial network may have been defected.

B. Self-Organizing Network (SON)

The SANSAs SON allows adapting the network topology to the traffic demands, routing the traffic to less congested links which results in a net capacity increase. It also provides the capability of skipping failed links for an improved network resilience. Note that in traditional daisy-chain terrestrial networks, the network is as robust as it is one of their links. Besides, the SON solution enables the use of energy aware routing algorithms capable of reducing the overall energy consumption by setting different network nodes in sleep mode during low demand traffic periods. Moreover, it reduces the need of an exhaustive radio planning of the whole network, which in turn reduces the operator CAPEX. The smart antennas also contribute to CAPEX reduction since they do not require complex antenna pointing at installation.

C. Spectrum coexistence of terrestrial and satellite segments

The capacity requirements can be partly translated to a demand of more spectra, which is already a scarce resource. Therefore, SANSAs will develop interference management techniques targeting the spectrum sharing among the terrestrial and satellite segments for optimizing its usage. In particular, the research efforts will be focused on Ka band where current CEPT recommendations [3] allow coexistence of terrestrial backhauling services at 18 GHz and 28 GHz and satellite-to-Earth and Earth-to-satellite satellite links, respectively.

III. SANSAs TECHNOLOGIES

The technologies that will make possible the proposed hybrid backhaul network can be split in two main groups discussed next.

A. Spectrum coexistence enabling technologies

SANSAs will investigate interference mitigation techniques at three main different levels in order to enable the spectrum coexistence of terrestrial and satellite segments. First, SANSAs will focus on beamforming techniques that will allow the simultaneous operation of terrestrial and satellite links by means of their different spatial locations. The basic idea is to equip terrestrial backhaul nodes with smart antennas capable of placing radiation nulls in the directions of the satellite terminals. Although beamforming is quite a mature technology, it has been not adopted in mobile backhaul, rather due to cost restrictions. Therefore, in SANSAs we will analyze different antenna beamforming networks and beamforming algorithms in order to propose a solution that maximizes the cost-performance trade-off. Among others, adaptive side-lobe suppression techniques based on auxiliary antenna arrays or array fed reflectors, combined with Least Mean Square (LMS), Recursive Least Squares (RLS) or Generalized Sidelobe Canceller (GSC) algorithms will be explored besides cost efficient hybrid analog-digital beamforming networks for

phased arrays. In addition, other antenna solutions not requiring complex feeding networks such as reconfigurable reflect arrays or metasurface antennas will be also considered.

Second, SANSAs project will develop smart dynamic radio resource management (RRM) techniques for the shared terrestrial-satellite networks which will maximize the system availability and capacity, while assuring that the QoS of both satellite and terrestrial links are not degraded by spectrum coexistence. Although dynamic RRM has been widely studied in terrestrial communications and rather less in satellite ones, SANSAs will explore ground-breaking solutions for the considered hybrid scenario.

Finally, SANSAs project will address database-assisted shared spectrum techniques. Static and dynamic information of the interfering transceivers such as location, transmit power and temporal spectrum activities will be stored in a database and used to efficiently manage the shared access to the spectrum. It must be noted that the static information will be easily obtained in this case due to the collaboration between satellite and terrestrial operators providing the same backhaul service.

B. Self-organizing hybrid network enabling technologies

The reconfiguration of the terrestrial network topology will be enabled by the smart antennas deployed in the terrestrial backhaul nodes as well. On top of that, SANSAs will develop disruptive management techniques for efficiently controlling the resources of the whole hybrid network and integrating satellite network decisions and routing of the terrestrial network. SANSAs will focus particularly in the interoperability of both satellite and terrestrial backhaul networks by designing self-organizing load-balancing algorithms that will aggregate the capacity offered by all terrestrial and satellite resources available at each backhaul node, thus allowing an overall capacity increase. Traffic routing algorithms will also target the reduction of the power consumption of the whole hybrid network. In all routing algorithms, special care of the delay introduced by the satellite links will be taken into account.

SANSAs will also investigate the combination Multicast beamforming (from the satellite towards the terrestrial distribution network) with efficient traffic routing in order to optimize the backhaul network throughput of the hybrid satellite-terrestrial system.

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